

Effect of Benzyl Isothiocyanate (BITC) on Morpho-physiological and Biochemical Aspects of *Cassia occidentalis* L.

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ABSTRACT

The present laboratory experimental study was carried about to evaluate the allelopathic potential of an allelochemical, benzyl-isothiocyanate (BITC) on some morpho-physiological and biochemical parameters of *Cassia occidentalis*. 2, 4, 6 $\times 10^{-4}$ M concentrations of BITC were applied to determine their effect on morpho-physiological parameters (seed germination, root length, shoot length, fresh weight, dry weight etc.) and biochemical parameters (chlorophyll, carotenoids, protein and α -amylase) of test plant under laboratory condition. Study was conducted on 10 day seedlings of *Cassia occidentalis*. Not only seedling growth parameters even the chlorophyll, carotenoids, protein and α -amylase were appreciably reduced, thereby indicating that BITC negatively affects the growth of *Cassia occidentalis*. The study was concluded that BITC possesses weed suppressing ability.

Key words: Allelopathy, Allelochemical, Weed, BITC, *Cassia occidentalis*

INTRODUCTION

Among the natural plant products, the allelochemicals create one of the major groups and provide allelopathic property to the donor plant, being biologically active. The allelopathic interactions, in general, and the allelochemicals, in particular, are regarded as an important tool for sustainable weed and pest management, and disease control (Singh *et al.*, 2001). The purified allelochemicals and /or their derivatives and even the compounds synthesized on their chemistry can be utilized as novel agrochemicals for sustainable management in an eco-friendly manner (Singh *et al.*, 2001). Allelochemicals represent a diversity of chemical nature. Papaya seeds were found to contain a powerful inhibitory agent, benzyl isothiocyanate (BITC). This compound, which is enzymatically derived from benzyl glucosinolate, is found in both the fruit and seeds of papaya in significant amounts (Chan *et al.*, 1978, Tang, 1971), composing up to 2% of the seeds by weight (Tang *et al.*, 1972). Additionally, it has been reported in the Cruciferae [for example, *Lepidium sativum* L. # LEPSA seeds contain approximately 1.7% BITC] (Daxenbichler *et al.*, 1964) and in several species of the genus *Tropaeolum* (family Tropaeolaceae) (Kjaer *et al.*, 1978). BITC has strong bactericidal, fungicidal, and insecticidal activities (Dem'yanenko *et al.*, 1973). Weeds are unwanted and undesirable plants that interfere with the utilization of land and water resources and thus, adversely affect crop production and human welfare. Weeds compete with

crop plants for nutrients, soil moisture, space and sunlight (Rajan and Sankaran, 1974). The world food loss due to weeds has been estimated to be about 11.5 percent of the total food production (Parker and Fryer, 1975).

Materials and Methods

Seeds of *Cassia occidentalis* were collected locally from wildy growing area of Distt. Muzaffarnagar. Benzyl isothiocyanate (BITC) was purchased from Sigma-aldrich, Germany.

Seeds were surface sterilized with 0.1% mercuric chloride. Seeds were dipped in distilled water for 24 h for imbibition prior to germination trials. These were then equidistantly placed in normal size petri dishes lined with two layers of moistened Whatman no.1 filter paper. The filter paper was treated with 2, 4, 6 $\times 10^{-4}$ M (T_1, T_2 and T_3 respectively) of Benzyl isothiocyanate (BITC). For each treatment three replicates were kept. A similar set up of three replicates without treatment served as control (T_0). The entire set up was kept in an environmentally controlled seed germinating chamber at 25⁰C and 75 % relative humidity with a photoperiod of 16/8 day/night. After 10 days, the number of seeds that germinated was counted, root length, shoot length, seedling fresh weight and dry weight were measured and the total chlorophyll, total carotenoids, total protein and α -amylase activity were estimated.

Results and Discussion

Morpho-physiological attributes of *Cassia occidentalis* were recorded in terms of % germination, root and shoot length, fresh and dry weight, vigour index, tolerance index and germination speed in different treatments of BITC. It is very clear from the results that in response to different concentrations of BITC, Germination was considerably reduced in compared to control (Fig.1). Reduction in germination was more at 6×10^{-4} M as

Table.1 Morpho-physiological attributes of 10 days old seedlings of *Cassia occidentalis* grown in different concentrations of BITC

Treatment (10^{-4} M)	% Germination	Root length	Shoot length	Fresh weight	Dry weight	% Moisture content	Vigour Index	Tolerance index	Germination speed
0	89.00±2.00	3.23±.029	7.03±0.42	76.33±2.1	7.07±0.23	90.74	913.14	100	22.25
2	82.66±3.06	3.03±0.42	6.53±0.15	77.00±2.0	7.20±0.20	90.64	790.22	93.8	20.66
4	73.33±3.06	2.27±0.32	5.77±0.25	70.13±1.1	6.67±0.12	90.49	589.57	70.27	14.66
6	53.33±3.51	0.87±0.42	3.03±0.75	53.40±3.1	5.60±0.20	89.5	207.98	26.93	7.61

compared to others. At the lowest concentration of 2×10^{-4} M BITC treatment, germination was reduced by about 7% while at, 4×10^{-4} M a reduction of over 17% was observed. A significantly inhibition of germination of the test weed was observed at a concentration of 6×10^{-4} M. The root length and shoot length of the test weed were significantly reduced at 2, 4 and 6×10^{-4} as compared to control (Fig.1). The fresh weight and dry weight of test weed was slightly increased at 2×10^{-4} M conc. but significant reduced in 6×10^{-4} M (30% and 20% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.1). % Moisture, vigour index, tolerance index and germination speed were also significantly reduced at different conc. as compared to control (Fig.1).

Biochemical attributes of *Cassia occidentalis* were recorded in terms of Chl.a, Chl.b, total chl., total carotenoides, total proteins and α -amylase activity. Chl.a was significantly reduced at conc. at 2, 4 and 6×10^{-4} M (12.91%, 19.86 and 32.78 % respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2). Similarly Chl.b was also significantly reduced at 2, 4 and 6×10^{-4} M conc. (14%, 42% and 68% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2). Similarly total chl. was also significantly reduced at all three conc. as compared to control (Fig.2). Total carotenoides were slightly reduced at lowest conc. but significantly reduced at 4 and 6×10^{-4} M conc. (10 % and 45% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2). Total protein was significantly increased at all three conc. (21%, 34% and 48% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2). α -amylase activity was appreciably reduced at lowest conc. but significantly reduced at 4 and 6×10^{-4} M (34%, and 59% respectively) as compared to control (Fig.2).

Table. 2 Biochemical attributes of 10 days old seedlings of *Cassia occidentalis* grown in different concentrations of BITC

Treatment (10 ⁻⁴ M)	Chl, a (mg/g fwt)	Chl, b (mg/g fwt)	Total Chl (mg/g fwt)	Total carotenoides (mg/g fwt±)	Protein (mg casein eq./g fwt±SD)	α-amylase (mg starch degraded/min/gfwt±SD)
0	0.302±0.004	0.261±0.008	0.563±0.004	0.432±0.006	40.14±1.48	48.03±1.49
2	0.263±0.001	0.223±0.018	0.486±0.019	0.419±0.001	48.68±2.56	45.20±1.04
4	0.242±0.008	0.149±0.018	0.391±0.010	0.386±0.002	53.80±2.56	31.68±0.88
6	0.203±0.008	0.083±0.004	0.285±0.011	0.237±0.005	59.78±1.48	19.66±0.60

Conclusion

It is clear from the present study that benzyl isothiocyanate (BITC) has a potential to reduce the some morpho-physiological parameters as well as biochemical parameters (germination, early growth and development of the weed species and thus could prove very useful for future weed management programmes.

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